

Factors for Developing Students' Communicative Competence through an Innovative Approach

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Abstract: This article discusses the development of university students' communicative competence through innovative approaches. It analyzes the importance of both existing and new, modern innovative technologies that need to be used in the educational process.

Keywords: communicative competence, innovative approach, intellectual development.

Our main goal is to ensure that young people have access to high-quality education, providing all the necessary conditions for them to realize their potential and talents. *President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. M. Mirziyoyev*

Developing communicative competence in university students is crucial for their academic success and future careers. Innovative approaches make this process more effective and engaging.

High-quality education today is evaluated by the development of communicative competence. Therefore, enhancing teacher-student interactions to a new level requires:

- Establishing friendly and effective communication between teachers and students.
- Recognizing that teacher-student communication is a critical component of continuous education.
- Addressing the need to adapt communication styles as the volume of information grows.
- Teachers' continual professional development, personal skills, and pedagogical expertise.
- Considering students' perspectives, interests, and needs in the educational process.
- Continuously updating teacher-student communication methods scientifically to ensure educational effectiveness.
- Teachers' command of language, interpersonal communication skills, problem-solving abilities, and psychological knowledge.

By meeting these criteria, students' communicative competence can be effectively developed. Communicative competence is essential for language learning, enabling effective interaction in various contexts. It is more than just a practical skill; it's a fundamental ability that allows us to communicate with each other and navigate the world.

Developing communicative skills further involves exposure to different communication styles and situations, like engaging with diverse media forms (books, films, news articles) and interacting with people from various backgrounds. This broadened exposure helps us understand the diverse ways language is used and interpreted. Moreover, technology, through social media, messaging, and video conferencing, plays a major role in shaping how students communicate. Using technology as a communication tool enhances our ability to express ourselves in a digital world.

Ethical considerations in communication, like respecting others' perspectives, understanding the impact of our words and actions, and practicing empathy, are essential for creating positive and inclusive communication environments.

Communicative competence encompasses the ability to convey and understand messages effectively across various contexts. It includes linguistic, sociolinguistic, speech, and strategic competencies. Developing communicative competence is crucial as it enables people to engage in meaningful conversations, manage social interactions, and succeed in academic and professional settings. Innovative language learning approaches, incorporating technology, interactive activities, and task-based methodologies, create an engaging and immersive learning environment. Teachers can encourage active participation, foster real communication, and provide opportunities for meaningful language practice, thereby enhancing students' communicative competence.

Innovative methodologies to enhance communicative competence offer promising ways to improve students' language skills and communication effectiveness. Integrating interactive activities, technology, and targeted feedback creates a dynamic learning experience that promotes communicative competence. Ongoing assessment and commitment to professional development are essential for advancing communicative competence pedagogy and ensuring steady progress in language learning. As educators address the evolving needs of language learners, the integration of innovative strategies will play a key role in shaping the future of communicative competence development.

Innovative Approaches:

➤ Enriching the Learning Process with Modern Technologies:

- ✓ *Online Platforms:* Using platforms like Moodle and Google Classroom to organize materials, assignments, discussions, and assessments.
- ✓ *Simulation Programs:* Utilizing simulation software to develop communication skills, such as virtual conversations or presentation practice programs.
- ✓ *Video Conferencing:* Organizing online communication among students via platforms like Zoom and Skype.
- ✓ *Educational Films and Videos:* Using educational films and videos to enhance learning and student interest.

➤ Applying Interactive Learning Methods:

- ✓ *Group Work:* Organizing students into groups and assigning tasks to help develop communication skills.
- ✓ *Role-Playing:* Assigning roles to students to enhance communication skills.
- ✓ *Debates:* Allowing students to express their opinions on various topics and interact with each other.
- ✓ *Open Discussions:* Enabling students to freely express their thoughts during class.

➤ **Using New Methods to Assess Communicative Competence:**

- ✓ *Portfolios*: Creating portfolios to showcase students' communication skills.
- ✓ *Projects*: Assigning group or individual projects to evaluate communication skills.
- ✓ *Online Tests*: Assessing students' communication skills through online tests.

➤ **Increasing Student Motivation:**

- ✓ *Making the Learning Process Interesting*: Making the learning process engaging and beneficial for students.
- ✓ *Encouraging Success*: Recognizing students' achievements and encouraging them.
- ✓ *Promoting Self-Study*: Motivating students to self-study and acquire new knowledge.

Example in Technical Universities:

- In technical English classes:
 - ✓ Teaching the vocabulary and grammar necessary for communicating with professionals in technical fields.
 - ✓ Training students to prepare and defend presentations on technical topics.
 - ✓ Teaching students to read and write technical documents.
- In engineering and technology classes:
 - ✓ Teaching students to present their technical projects understandably to others.
 - ✓ Developing collaboration skills through group projects.
- Involving industry partners in the educational process:
 - ✓ Conducting practical sessions with industry partners.
 - ✓ Organizing discussions between students and industry partners.

Conclusion: Applying innovative approaches helps develop students' communicative competence in technical universities. This enables them to effectively apply their knowledge and skills, succeed academically, and achieve professional success in the future.

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